

ISic4391

Sikel funerary inscription

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

none

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euboia

Place of origin (modern)

Licodia Eubea

Provenance

Necropolis at contrada Vigna della Signora; found October 1920, together with a second inscribed piece (ISic3363) and two uninscribed blocks

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 42 cm

Width 97 cm

Depth 30 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἀδατοι

Apparatus

Text after Orsi

Translation

Commentary

the sole record of this text is the note by Orsi in the inventory to ISic3363 (Museo P.Orsi inv. 41697), recording it alongside that piece, but noting that it was not recovered. Paino transcribes Orsi's report and drawing

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Paino, Emma 1958. Nuova iscrizione sicula. *Kokalos*. 4: 163-168.

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Drawing of P.Orsi, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014